

THE EVALUATION OF REMOTE AUDITING ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE SCOPE OF FACTORS AFFECTING INDEPENDENT AUDIT QUALITY: A QUALITATIVE RESEARCH

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Abstract

The use of information and communication technology (ICT) in auditing has increased over time. Developments in ICT have played an important role in the transition to the remote audit model. Auditing practices have experienced a digital transformation with a rapid transition towards remote auditing, which has been mandated as a result of social restrictions due to the pandemic in recent years. The aim of this study is to examine remote auditing and evaluate its impact on the quality of independent audits. Factors affecting audit quality are categorized as audited entity, independent audit firm, independent auditor, use of information technology, legal regulations, and institutions. The study, which used qualitative data methods, applied descriptive analysis. Research on the evaluation of remote auditing activities, within the framework of factors affecting independent audit quality, was conducted through interviews with eight independent auditors. The interviews revealed that to become a leader in remote auditing practices, it is necessary to establish a remote auditing culture. The Public Oversight Authority, which is authorised in the field of independent auditing, should take on its regulatory role regarding remote auditing practices. Additionally, remote auditing practices should be experienced through simulation training.

Keywords: Audit, Independent Audit, Remote Audit, Audit Quality, Independent Auditor.

1. INTRODUCTION

Independent audits provide investors with confidence in the accuracy of financial statements, thereby increasing transparency and accountability in capital markets. The opinions of independent auditors, who are responsible for obtaining reasonable assurance that the financial statements are free from material misstatement, are important for users of financial statements.

The advancements in information and communication technology have impacted the field of auditing, as well as all areas of life, leading to the development of new approaches. The global Covid-19 pandemic has resulted in social restrictions worldwide, greatly affecting both business and daily life.

Consequently, auditing, like all fields, has begun a technology-oriented process. During the pandemic, remote auditing has replaced traditional auditing as a viable alternative to perform the audit profession without disruption (Litzenberg & Ramirez, 2020: 2).

Although the pandemic is over, work and daily life continue to be redefined with strategies implemented during the pandemic. In the post-epidemic period, businesses are redefining the way of living, working, and doing business based on the strategies implemented during the pandemic. Academic studies have shown that enterprises actively use remote audit processes (Koerniawati, 2021: 1135). Remote auditing practices are expected to become more widespread due to their high benefit/cost ratio, meeting the requirements of relevant parties (Ghosh & Abeywardhane, 2021: 301). Although not a new practice, auditors have historically implemented remote auditing practices due to benefits such as scope expansion, timing flexibility, and cost reduction in the audit process (Li et al., 2023: 130). Prior to the pandemic, only 2% of audits were conducted remotely. However, in 2020, this figure increased to 38%, and in 2021, the proportion of remote or hybrid audits rose to 79% (Aivazi, 2022).

Auditing involves communicating with auditees, reviewing documents and records, and making observations. Conducting these activities remotely has resulted in significant changes to the audit process, leading to changes in the workload of auditors and audit supervision. Furthermore, auditors are obligated to accurately evaluate risks and demonstrate professional scepticism throughout the audit. However, the absence of physical presence during remote audits hinders auditors' ability to exercise adequate professional scepticism (Sorensen and Ortegren, 2021: 41).

Remote auditing has become increasingly common in the auditing profession. However, there are currently no effective regulations guiding remote auditing, nor any scientific studies that systematically examine how the transition from on-site to remote auditing affects audit success. This study examines the inadequacy of regulations related to remote auditing activities, which have been widely applied recently, and the lack of research systematically examining how the transition from traditional auditing to remote auditing affects audit success. The study provides a theoretical analysis of the concepts of remote auditing and audit quality. Subsequently, the study quotes and interprets the findings obtained through the semi-structured interview method to evaluate remote auditing in terms of audit quality. The study aims to bridge the gap in this field and provide a foundation for future research.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Remote Auditing

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to the widespread adoption of remote inspection applications. Worldwide travel restrictions have made it difficult or impossible to conduct traditional auditing. However, the need for auditing remains (Castka and Searcy, 2023: 5-6). During the pandemic, auditors have generally conducted traditional auditing practices online using video conferencing technologies such as Skype, Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Go-To Meeting, WebEx, and Lync. The pandemic has led to an increased adoption of communication technologies and applications, which has impacted the redesign of audit practices. However, conducting traditional audit practices online during this period was insufficient to be considered a fully remote audit activity (Castka et al., 2021: 5).

Audit firms have used remote auditing activities in situations where the audited entity was remote or dangerous even before the pandemic. In cases where traditional auditing was not possible, auditors carried out audit activities using various applications. Some auditors employed unmanned aerial vehicles equipped with video cameras to remotely inspect pipelines, water tanks, or other hard-to-reach areas (Rinaldi, 2019).

To fully comprehend the concept of remote auditing, it is necessary to explain the concept of traditional auditing. A traditional audit typically begins with a review of documents, records, or business measurements. The process then requires auditors to conduct on-site audit practices such as analytical tests, observations, and interviews (Byrnes et al., 2018). At the end of the traditional audit process, the auditor prepares an audit report, which focuses on assessing whether the requirements have been met (Castka and Searcy, 2023: 6).

Remote auditing is a technique used to examine the degree of achievement of predetermined objectives in the digital field. The findings obtained from these examinations are then shared. This audit technique proposes the use of technology to carry out audit activities in the digital field (Koç, 2021: 249). Remote auditing refers to the use of information and communication technologies to carry out audits in the digital field. This eliminates the need for physical communication with customers when determining the accuracy of financial data, collecting evidence, and conducting data analytics (Teeter et al., 2011: 2).

2.2. Audit Quality

Enterprises must have their financial reports approved by an impartial person or organization outside the enterprise to demonstrate that they are prepared in a fair and reliable manner. This practice is crucial for the prestige and reliability of enterprises in the market (Süklüm, 2020: 18). Auditing is the process of examining economic transactions to determine if they meet predetermined criteria. Evidence is collected and evaluated independently, and the results are communicated to relevant parties (Güredin, 2000: 5). Accounting audit is the process of obtaining evidence to provide reasonable assurance regarding an entity's financial statements and other required disclosures conforming to specified standards. It involves checking, evaluating, and reporting on conformity with independent auditing standards (Kaval, 2008: 10).

The quality of an audit is determined by the ability to carry out independent auditing activities with the necessary qualifications to ensure that accounting information is presented impartially, accurately, and independently to those concerned (Ada & Yardımçioğlu, 2017: 1732). The opinions of independent auditors and the level of confidence in their opinions are linked to the quality of the audit (Oktay, 2013: 47). Different interest groups in the audit process may define audit quality differently. For financial statement users, audit quality is defined as the absence of material misleading or inaccurate information in the financial statements. For auditors, audit quality is defined as the complete fulfillment of all tasks in the audit process by the audit firm. For lawmakers, audit quality is defined as the adherence to certain rules and standards during audit activities (Knechel et al., 2013: 385-386).

Although the concept of audit quality is expressed differently by various interest groups involved in audit activities, it is important to evaluate each statement within the scope of factors that affect quality. Ada and Yardımcıoğlu (2017) conducted a literature review on the factors affecting audit quality and categorised them into five groups. When defining quality, it is important to consider the five groups of factors that have been identified through evaluations from various interest groups. These factors have been determined through the collection and analysis of data from academic studies, and are considered to be comprehensive in this field. The literature has classified the factors that affect the quality of independent audits in various ways. The five groups identified have enabled the factors affecting quality to be summarised under main headings.

This text discusses the factors that affect the quality of independent audits. These factors include:

- The audited entity,
- The independent audit firm,
- The independent auditor,
- The use of information technology and
- Legal regulations and institutions.

3. METHOD

3.1. Research Methodology

The study employed qualitative research, which is a subjective-interpretive process of examining events and perceptions using qualitative data collection methods such as observation, interview, document analysis, and audio-visual materials to solve a problem (Creswell, 2020: 159). This method is suitable for researching topics that are not well-known using a limited number of samples (De Ruyter & Scholl, 1998: 8). Qualitative research is characterised by its naturalistic approach and lack of hypothesis formation. This method allows for the formation of understanding and theory through experiences gained in field studies (Akdemir & Kılıç, 2021: 488).

The research strategy in qualitative research is determined by patterns. The study employed phenomenology as a qualitative research design. The study employs a phenomenological design to explore the individual's experience of evaluating remote supervision in terms of audit quality. The study employs a phenomenological design to explore the individual's experience of evaluating remote supervision in terms of audit quality. This approach aims to provide an in-depth understanding of how participants perceive the phenomenon based on their real experiences. The language used is clear, objective, and value-neutral, with a formal register and precise word choice. The text adheres to conventional academic structure and formatting, with consistent citation and footnote style. The sentences and paragraphs create a logical flow of information with causal connections between statements. The text is free from grammatical errors, spelling mistakes, and punctuation errors. No changes in content have been made. This design

was used to enable participants to share their experiences in remote supervision. The study aimed to investigate the subject in depth using a small number of participants.

3.2. Data Collection Method and Analysis

The study evaluated the impact of remote audit activities on independent audit quality using a semi-structured interview technique. The researcher prepared a pre-planned form with questions and directed them to the participants during the interviews. Participants were asked to provide detailed answers when necessary (Yüksel, 2020: 549).

For qualitative research, the sample size can range from one to twelve individuals (Patton, 1990: 169). In this study, we conducted interviews with eight independent auditors from Ankara who have at least ten years of professional experience and have practiced remote auditing. The data for this study were collected through remote interviews. The research included independent auditors who agreed to be interviewed and have over 10 years of professional experience, as well as those who perform remote auditing practices. The data was analysed using a descriptive approach. To maintain ethical standards, the names of the participants were kept confidential and coded as 'D1', 'D2', and so on.

3.3. Ethics, Limitations and Validity of the Study

The use of the semi-structured interview method in research requires ethical examination. The research details were examined by the İnönü University Social and Human Sciences Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee, and the research was deemed ethically appropriate with the decision dated 28.12.2023. The decision is provided in Appendix-1.

The research included independent auditors who performed remote auditing activities. Therefore, the research is limited to auditors who do not perform remote auditing activities. Additionally, the research is limited to members of the profession practicing in Ankara.

To ensure credibility and acceptance of the research, it is important to establish a certain level of reliability and validity in qualitative research. Baltacı (2019: 380) notes that while there are various methods for measuring validity and reliability in quantitative research, it is not possible to determine these factors in qualitative research. However, it is expected that qualitative researchers take necessary precautions to ensure the validity of their information and provide a clear and detailed description of their research process and data for evaluation by other researchers (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016: 284-285). To ensure the validity of the research data obtained from interviews, participant opinions were presented through direct quotations.

4. FINDINGS

The independent auditors' interview questions are analysed under five headings: (i) The quality of independent audit is affected by various factors, including the evaluation of remote audit practices in the context of the audited entity. (ii) Similarly, the evaluation of remote audit practices in the context of the independent audit firm is also a factor affecting

the quality of independent audit. (iii) Additionally, the evaluation of remote audit practices in the context of the independent auditor is another factor that affects the quality of independent audit. (iv) This section evaluates the impact of information technology on the quality of independent audits, specifically in relation to remote audit practices. (v) Additionally, this section evaluates the impact of legal regulations and institutions on the quality of independent audits, specifically in relation to remote audit practices.

Under the heading of audited entity, the factors affecting the quality of independent audit include entity size, corporate governance structure, and management support. Under the heading of independent audit firm, this section includes all factors that affect the quality of the audit, such as the audit team, audit process, audit fee, auditor rotation, audit report, audit plan and programme, and audit policies and procedures. Under the heading of independent auditor, all factors that affect quality related to the auditor are included. These factors include the auditor's professional training, competence, experience, care, diligence, independence, objectivity, and sectoral expertise. Under the heading of 'Use of Information Technology', this section includes all factors related to information technology that affect quality, such as the technological infrastructure and usage level of the audited entity, the technological infrastructure and usage level of the audit firm, and the auditor's level of use of information technology. Under the section of legal regulations and institutions, this text includes all factors that affect quality, such as auditing standards and the Public Oversight Accounting and Auditing Standards Authority (POA). Table-1 displays the determinations and suggestions of independent auditors who participated in the remote auditing activities.

Table 1: Quality Issues and Solutions for Remote Control Applications

Factors Affecting Independent Audit Quality	Remote Audit Activities - The Current Situation	Recommendations for Quality Remote Audit Activities
Audited Enterprise	Perception of lack of control and cyber security concern due to the lack of physical interaction in remote control applications	Establishing and promoting a culture of remote auditing.
Independent Audit Firm	Lack of experience with remote control applications.	Establishing suitable conditions for remote audit applications and defining the methods and procedures to be employed.
Independent Auditor	Willing in remote control applications but insufficient in terms of knowledge and experience	Experience of remote control applications through simulation training
Use of Information Technology	Advanced independent auditing software is not widely available.	Ownership of information technology infrastructure and its use in applications that reduce cybersecurity risk.
Legal Regulations and Institutions	There is a Public Oversight Authority authorized to work digitally, but studies for remote audit applications are insufficient	Public Oversight Authority to take on the role of regulator for remote auditing applications

The table presents aggregated and summarised information obtained from interviews with independent auditors. Details of the interviews for each factor are provided under subheadings.

4.1. Evaluation of Remote Audit Applications in The Context of the Audited Enterprise from Factors Affecting Independent Audit Quality

The quality of independent audits is influenced by various factors. These include the size of the audited entity, its corporate governance structure, and management support. Professional management and a strong corporate governance approach can enhance the effectiveness of independent audits. Utku and Kaya (2022: 29) suggest that the awareness of independent audits by managers and employees, as well as their cooperation in facilitating the audit process, can have a positive impact on audit quality. Additionally, Bekçi and Gör (2016) found that the dissemination of corporate governance practices can lead to higher quality audit activities. Eddine (2015) based their audit on the size of the entity and argued that as the entity size increases, so does the state audit, resulting in improved audit quality.

The independent auditors' evaluations of remote audit practices in the context of factors affecting the quality of independent audits, such as audited entity size, corporate governance structure, and management support, are as follows:

Participant D1: "It is easier and more reliable to obtain the requested information and documents from institutionalised firms. Since large companies have previous audit experience, senior management's support for audit practices is more supportive".

Participant D2: "The starting point of remote audit is the audited entity. The perspective of the auditee towards remote audit is the main determinant of the quality of remote audit. If the auditee is ready for remote auditing and supports remote auditing, successful results are obtained. In addition, the organisational structure of the audited entity and the management's support for the audit are important. In remote audit quality, the size of the audited entity is generally considered positive".

Participant D3: "The audited entity has a very important share in the quality of independent audit. Undoubtedly, the same statement is valid for remote audit. It is essential to collect audit evidence from the audited entity in the remote conduct of the independent audit activity. Firms that do not have remote auditing experience or are not ready for remote auditing may lead the process to a dead end. Instead of speeding up and facilitating the audit activities, the expected benefits may not be obtained due to the audited entity.

If the audited enterprise has a large or corporate structure, it can relatively adapt to remote auditing activities. On the other hand, it is very difficult to break the classical audit perception and habits in small and family business type audited enterprises. The beginning of quality in the conduct of remote audit work is the profile of the audited enterprise".

Participant D4: "There is a perception among our colleagues above a certain age that distance audit practices will have a negative impact on the quality of independent audit. On the other hand, there is a widespread belief among our young colleagues that distance education is better and of higher quality. In addition, remote working culture has become widespread with the Covid -19 process. Remote auditing practices may cause cyber security concerns in companies that do not have experience in remote auditing, interviews in remote auditing take a lot of time and do not provide as effective communication as face-to-face meetings, they do not feel like they are being audited in remote auditing, they are hesitant to convey some information to the auditor in remote auditing, and these issues are criticised. However, it is also stated that they have gained serious benefits in terms of reduced costs without time losses such as travelling, expenses and waiting".

Participant D5: "If the auditee is a large and corporate company, the quality of the remote audit work generally increases. The fact that the management of the enterprise is favourable to the audit and accepts the audit activity increases the audit quality. On the contrary, the quality of remote audit remains low in the audited company model, which can be considered as a small, family firm. In addition, the fact that the management is distant from the remote audit issue further reduces the quality. In order to increase the quality of remote auditing, firstly, the remote auditing experience of the companies in this field should increase. Since remote working and digitalisation gained momentum after the Covid-19 process, it is possible to claim that these experiences are not sufficiently formed".

Participant D6: "The auditee is the starting point for the digitalisation of independent audit work. If the auditee is not prepared for remote auditing, it will make it difficult for remote auditing to be of high quality. The independent audit culture has been established in large and corporate firms since the 1980s. There are approximately 400 independent audit firms authorised by the POA and approximately 10,000 audited firms. The number of these firms with an independent audit culture is around 30 per cent. The remaining 70 per cent do not have an independent audit culture, let alone remote auditing. In an environment with such a limited number of companies, the quality of remote auditing starts 1-0 behind in terms of the audited entity".

Participant D7: "Since remote auditing activities are not yet widely applied today, the auditee's approach to this process is very important. The internal control chain applied in the audited entity, advanced technological applications, positive experiences and approaches of senior management regarding the audit process can be listed among the factors that increase the quality of remote auditing.

Participant D8: "The auditee's approach to the audit process is very important in remote audit practices. The technological infrastructure of the enterprise, the management's approach to audit activities, the establishment and implementation of an effective internal control system in the enterprise, etc. factors provide convenience to the independent audit company in the remote audit process and increase the quality of the audit".

The opinions of the participants regarding their suggestions in the context of "audited enterprise" are as follows:

Participant D4: "It can be said that the quality perceptions of the audited enterprises in remote auditing are sometimes positive and sometimes negative, and each enterprise has a perception depending on its own structure. It can be suggested that the remote auditing experience should be extended to the audited enterprises".

Participant D7: "In order to increase the quality of remote auditing, training and explanatory videos about the methods and practices that can be followed by both the enterprises subject to audit and independent auditors can be published to increase and spread the awareness of remote auditing".

4.2. Evaluation of Remote Audit Practices in The Context of Independent Audit Firm Among the Factors Affecting Independent Audit Quality

The quality of independent audits in the context of an independent audit firm can be affected by various factors, including rotation, audit team, audit process, and audit fees. Low audit fees may result in inadequate and careless audits, while high audit fees may compromise auditor independence (Stanley and DeZoort, 2007: 131). Shafie et al. (2009) discovered a significant positive correlation between audit firm size and audit report quality.

Karahan and Çukacı (2018) discovered that the professional scepticism of the audit team has a positive impact on the quality of the independent audit. Similarly, Özger and Tuğay (2020) found that rotation in auditing has a positive effect on auditor independence and audit quality.

The independent auditors' evaluations of remote auditing practices in the context of factors affecting independent audit quality, such as the audit team, audit process, audit fee, auditor rotation, audit report, audit plan and programme, and audit policies and procedures, are presented below:

Participant D1: "Remote audit can be implemented more easily in audit firms with strong audit staff and high audit fees. These firms are generally able to allocate more budget and resources for the infrastructure elements such as computer software etc. required for remote audit firms".

Participant D2: "In remote auditing, the independent audit firm plays a leading role in the formation of quality. With the increase in the number of independent audit firms specialised in this field, quality will increase even more. The independent audit firm develops practices and methods to increase quality in remote auditing. In addition, measures should be taken to ensure that independent audit risks do not increase in remote audit practices".

Participant D3: "The second factor in ensuring quality in remote audit work is the independent audit firm. The fact that this organisation has remote audit experience, procedures and culture will increase the audit quality".

Participant D4: "Independent audit firms assume a proactive role in remote audit practices. The digitalisation and artificial intelligence network push independent audit firms to work in this direction. It is considered that remote auditing has many benefits in terms of independent audit quality. Remote auditing saves time in an effective and efficient audit work. Harmonisation between audit teams accelerates the audit process. Audit plans and programmes are carried out by computer software. These softwares are not yet at a level to enable the effective execution of remote audits. Remote audit trainings and simulations that will increase the harmonisation of audit teams are being conducted. Audit companies try to increase their remote audit experience and learn lessons from the process".

Participant D5: "The institutional determinant of the quality of remote audit work is the independent audit organisation. These organisations create the necessary infrastructure for remote audit in independent audit.

They increase the quality of independent remote auditing by creating an appropriate combination of technologies such as computers and software. Independent audit firms determine the factors such as time, labour force and finance to be allocated for remote audit. As the independent audit organisation sees the benefits of remote auditing, it will provide more opportunities in this field".

Participant D6: "In the digitalisation of independent audit activities, the audit organisation can be compared to a car. A good vehicle will make the journey of good quality. The independent audit organisation should be able to provide a quality environment suitable for remote audit to the independent audit staff. The independent audit organisation can create a structure that can affect the quality of remote audit in terms of budget, monitoring and management support.

Independent audit organisations, like the audited entity, have not had enough experience in remote auditing. Audit organisations other than large, corporate and bridge audit organisations have mostly met with the concept of remote auditing in the Covid-19 and later period. For this reason, independent audit organisations are just now encountering documents such as sufficient standards, unity of practice, and critical issues to be considered in this field".

Participant D7: "Although the audit will be managed remotely, in order for the audit activity to be successful and of high quality, audit firms should prepare and monitor the entire programme related to the establishment of the audit strategy, planning the audit process, conducting, completing and reporting the work. Independent audit firms should determine the methods and procedures to be implemented in this process".

Participant D8: "Today, there is no standardised road map regarding the ways and methods to be followed in the remote audit process. Therefore, the previous audit experience of the audit firms that will perform the remote audit, the experience, discipline and professional development of the independent auditors of the company increase the quality of the audit and contribute to reducing the audit risk as much as possible".

The opinions of the participants regarding their suggestions in the context of "independent audit firm" are as follows:

Participant D3: "Independent audit firms should allocate a budget for the costs to be incurred for quality. Not only the budget is not enough, but they should also ensure that the necessary trainings are received by the audit teams. By providing more procedures, forms, work instructions and experience sharing environment, it can create a structure suitable for increasing quality".

Participant D4: "It is necessary to add remote audit mode to audit software, and regulations and guidelines should be made regarding digital working papers and the use of digital signatures. In addition, it can be suggested that audit firms should prepare a remote audit quality guide and determine the procedures and details in advance".

4.3. Evaluation of Remote Auditing Practices in The Context of Independent Auditor Among the Factors Affecting Independent Audit Quality

Another crucial factor that affects audit quality is the qualifications of the auditors who conduct independent audit activities. To become an independent auditor, one must complete the basic education and internship required by the profession. Additionally, auditors should possess professional curiosity, be sceptical, follow current legislation, take responsibility, and act in accordance with professional ethics. The quality of an audit is directly affected by the characteristics of the auditor. Independent and impartial behaviour during audit activities has a significant impact on audit quality. The effectiveness of audit reports relies on the auditor's ability to act independently. Familiarity with the structure of the sectors in which audited companies operate, as well as the auditor's previous experience in these sectors, can help the auditor identify sector-specific risks and detect errors and fraud. Sectoral specialisation can increase audit quality, as argued by Utku and Kaya (2022: 28). According to Gul et al. (2013), auditor competence and independence are key factors in determining audit quality. Therefore, it can be concluded that auditor independence is crucial for ensuring high-quality audits. Aslanoğlu and Baskan (2016) also found that audit reports prepared by independent auditors are of higher quality and more effective.

The independent auditors' evaluations of remote auditing practices in the context of factors affecting the quality of independent audit, such as professional training and competence, experience, attention and care, independence and objectivity, and sectoral expertise, are presented below:

Participant D1: "When remote auditing is evaluated from the point of view of the independent auditor; firstly, independent auditors who compete with time in traditional audits can complete the independent audit process effectively and efficiently by using remote auditing applications in order to alleviate the increasing workload in recent years. However, internet addiction may lead to the phenomenon of remote auditing professional burnout in some of the independent auditors who work devotedly 24/7 to keep up with the work".

Participant D2: "It should be said that the quality of remote auditing is directly related to the training and experience of the independent auditor".

Participant D3: "The manpower and labour that carry out remote audit work is provided by the independent auditor. The independent auditor is the most important element in conducting independent audit work remotely and has a direct impact on audit quality. Independent auditors create a certain remote audit culture by transferring their remote audit experiences to each other".

Participant D4: "It is seen that independent auditors who are familiar with computer technologies have adapted to remote auditing. Moreover, some auditors develop their own remote auditing techniques. Remote auditing has advantages in terms of auditor independence. In terms of impartiality, remote auditing gives a neutral image. Demand for remote auditing or e-auditing training, as it is known in the sector, is high. It can be said that the process will accelerate further with the increase in studies such as books and articles in this field. Training, seminars and symposiums are needed to increase the quality in the field of e-auditing. Remote auditing is an area where the independent auditor should show maximum professional attention and care. There are no established practices for the use of new remote audit tools such as metaverse meetings. As the number of independent auditors working in the field of remote auditing increases, the sector is expected to grow. "e-audit" trainings are provided for independent auditors within SÜRGEN (Turkish Union of Chamber of Private Accountants and Certified Public Accountants Advisers Continuing Professional Development Training Center) – TÜRMOB (Turkish Union of Chamber of Private Accountants and Certified Public Accountants). In addition, the Ministry of Finance is popularising remote auditing in tax audit with the "e-viz" application".

Participant D5: "In remote independent audit, the independent auditor should transform into a remote independent auditor. The success of this transformation will increase the quality of remote independent audit. The primary factor for the independent auditor to become a remote independent auditor is training. Independent auditors should be trained in this field. As the training on remote auditing increases, the quality-reducing procedures and errors of independent auditors in remote auditing will decrease. Independent auditors are currently trying to learn and perceive remote auditing with their own efforts".

Participant D6: "The independent auditor can be compared to the driver of the car on the road in remote audit quality. The more professional and experienced the driver of the car is, the better quality the journey will be. Since the independent auditor is the person who actually carries out the remote audit activities, his/her characteristics such as education and experience can also be very effective on quality. In remote auditing, the auditor's command of information technologies is important. It is noticeable that there is an excessive demand for trainings on this subject. The main reason for this is that the trainings in this field are very few and usually have limited number of participants".

Participant D7: "In remote auditing practices, the auditor's professional training and experience, commitment to basic ethical principles, ability to question and evaluate, and especially the professional use of today's developing technologies by the auditor are

among the factors that increase audit quality. In addition, conducting the audit process remotely has positive results in terms of minimising threats such as proximity-trust, bias-defence, which are among the factors that undermine the independence of the auditor, and contributes to the minimisation of audit costs for the enterprises".

Participant D8: "In order to increase the quality of the remote audit process, the auditor's professional training and experience, professional behaviour, and approach to basic ethical principles are very important. In addition, the auditor's superior use of contemporary technologies will contribute to reducing the time cost of the audit and conducting the remote audit process in a professional manner".

The opinions of the participants regarding their suggestions in the context of "independent auditor" are as follows:

Participant D2: Questions about remote auditing should be asked in independent auditing exams, remote auditing courses should be increased in continuing education. Books, articles and courses in this field should be increased. Remote auditing, which is preferred because it is easy and reduces costs and workload, should not increase the risks of independent auditing. In short, risk - cost - benefit balance should be established.

Participant D3: "In the field of remote auditing, independent auditors are open to all sources of information such as books, courses and seminars. The first demands of independent auditors in terms of continuing education are the use of digital technologies and artificial intelligence in auditing".

Participant D4: "E-audit trainings for independent auditors should be increased. Books, articles, thesis studies should be increased in this field. In the continuing education of independent auditors, e-auditing course should be made an annual obligation".

Participant D6: "In remote auditing, it is clear that ensuring the coordination of the independent audit team, obtaining remote work as audit evidence and preparing digital working papers will have an impact on quality".

4.4. Evaluation of Remote Audit Practices in The Context of Use of Information Technology Among the Factors Affecting Independent Audit Quality

Nowadays, organisations are capable of generating financial information in real-time and online. The use of information technology (IT) has revolutionised the way audit data is stored, collected, and utilised. IT encompasses hardware, software, communication, and network technology, which auditors utilise in the audit process to ensure audit quality (Ismanidar et al., 2022: 12).

It is crucial that auditors have adequate equipment for the audit and related activities. Auditors must keep up with technological advancements, assess their applicability in auditing, and continuously improve themselves accordingly (Güngör Karyağdı, 2022: 22). Manita et al. (2020) argued that digitalisation will increase the quality of audits by enabling auditors to analyse client data. They also suggest that this will lead to the formation of a new auditor profile.

The independent auditors' evaluations of remote auditing practices in the context of factors affecting the quality of independent audit, such as the use of information technology (including technological infrastructure and usage levels of the audited entity, audit firm, and auditor), are presented below:

Participant D1: "The quality of remote audit is directly related to training in information technology and predisposition to information technologies. It should not be forgotten that it is critical for quality that audit teams experienced in information technologies transfer their knowledge, documents and experience to assistant auditors and other relevant audit team members. In remote auditing, information technologies should be used in a way to minimise cyber security risks".

Participant D2: "The hardware and software capacity to be used in remote audit is important for quality. In general, audit firms invest in information technologies as long as they see the benefits. The information infrastructure is as important as the techniques used in remote auditing. The opportunities provided by information technologies play a key role in transferring a certain part of independent audit to remote audit environment.

Participant D3: "The use of information technologies is necessary in conducting remote audit activities. It is seen that these technologies are constantly developing due to Moore's Law. All these developments necessitate the continuous monitoring of information technologies. Only having the technology will not be effective on quality. At the same time, it is also necessary to be able to use these technologies in a way to do justice to them".

Participant D4: "Independent audit software is not yet as common and developed as accounting software. Office software is frequently and intensively used in the sector. In these office software, calculations, formulae and macros are written by independent auditors. Independent auditors have been using information technologies for many years, although not as much as an information auditor.

For this reason, there is an interest in information technologies in the sector. The server system, network structure, databases used by the audited entity are perceived and evaluated by independent auditors. Audit firms may be reluctant to invest in information technologies due to low audit fees and high competition in the sector. Auditors are generally positive about the fact that the use of information technologies saves time, increases efficiency and lightens the workload. They try to direct audit firms to invest in information technologies".

Participant D5: "In remote independent audit, information technology can be seen as one of the physical and infrastructural factors of independent audit quality. The use of information technology is directly related to technological infrastructure. Good hardware, software and computer structure may be important for quality. The level of the independent auditor's use of information technologies is currently not measured and questioned. Inadequate IT infrastructure in independent audit may also cause various cyber security weaknesses".

Participant D6: "We can liken information technologies to the road in the quality of remote audit. In a journey, the smoother and better maintained the road is, the more comfortable the journey will be and possible accident risks will be minimised. Therefore, the quality of the remote audit will be directly proportional to the independent auditors' ability to use information technologies quickly, effectively and professionally".

Participant D7: "Day by day developing technology has made the widespread use of information technologies a necessity for remote independent auditing as in many sectors. In this context, adopting these technologies for audited entities and independent audit firms creates positive effects in terms of time and cost savings in the audit process. As the use of information technologies by both independent audit firms and audited entities becomes professionalised, work efficiency will increase and business processes will become easier".

Participant D8: "Independent auditors in the sector follow today's technologies and try to apply these technologies with their own means and efforts. Audited entities, on the other hand, tend to need and invest more in information technologies as their size, business volume and profitability increase".

The opinions of the participants regarding their suggestions in the context of "use of information technology" are as follows:

Participant D2: "Since the field of informatics is one of the areas where independent auditors have difficulty in following the developments, the employment of computer engineers in companies should be made compulsory".

Participant D3: "Understanding and using information technologies requires a certain level of training and familiarity. My recommendation is that remote auditing and information technologies should be included as a course in POA (Public Oversight Authority) exams".

Participant D4: "It may be useful to have questions on information technologies in independent auditor exams. Like the Ministry of Finance, the POA (Public Oversight Authority) may grant licences to independent audit software and request that notifications and reports be made by these software".

Participant D6: "Providing both theoretical and practical training to independent auditors on information technologies is useful and will increase the spread of remote auditing. In addition, the effective use of these technologies will add positive value to independent audit firms in terms of both cost and time savings".

Participant D7: "Providing training to independent auditors on the use of information technologies will be a useful approach in terms of increasing the quality of remote auditing".

Participant D8: "In order to increase the quality, both companies and independent audit firms should invest in technological infrastructures and independent auditors should be provided with theoretical and practical training on IT activities".

4.5. Evaluation of Remote Auditing Practices in The Context of Legal Regulations and Institutions Among the Factors Affecting Independent Audit Quality

Auditing independent audit firms and subjecting the sector to legal regulations can improve the quality of audit activities. In Turkey, the Public Oversight Authority (POA) is responsible for auditing audit firms (Utku and Kaya, 2022: 29).

The independent auditors' evaluations of remote auditing practices in the context of factors affecting the quality of independent auditing, such as legal regulations and institutions (auditing standards, Public Oversight Accounting and Auditing Standards Authority, etc.), are presented below:

Participant D1: "POA has only recently been authorised to work digitally and only manages electronic financial reporting and contract notification applications in terms of remote auditing. A training regulation or any study on remote auditing provided by the POA has not been presented to the independent audit community. In addition, a fee tariff for remote auditing has not been published. File formats, checklists, samples of reports and working papers are expected to be presented by the POA. There is no direct Turkish and comprehensible standard in the auditing standards yet".

Participant D2: "Standards, rules, procedures, sample applications for remote auditing should be published by the POA. Ensuring quality and minimising risks in remote auditing is primarily the duty of the POA. Unless legal arrangements are made, there will be no healthy development in this field".

Participant D3: "The organisation that can be the leader in remote audit quality is POA. Although it has been authorised for digital working papers, there is no original work on remote auditing yet. However, for the development of remote auditing, legal regulations, standards, are strongly needed".

Participant D4: "In November 2022, POA was authorised for "digital working papers" and "information systems audit" for remote audit practices. However, it has not taken any steps in these areas until this date. The need for regulations such as digital working paper, digital audit contract, digital audit report is at the highest point in the sector".

Participant D5: "The weakest issue in remote independent audit is legal regulations and institutions. Since it is relatively new, the standards, rules and regulations for remote independent audit are not yet clear. The work carried out in remote independent auditing is currently carried out with the experience and dedication of independent auditors. Independent audit report and independent auditor's contract notifications are reported online to POA within the scope of electronic financial reporting. Working papers, audit files, independent audit report still have to be used in paper environment with wet signature".

Participant D6: "We can liken legal regulations and institutions to the speed limit on the road or the traffic police on duty in the quality of remote audit. In this context, necessary regulations, rules and procedures should be established by POA in order to manage and finalise the remote audit process in a quality and effective manner."

Participant D7: "Currently, there is no directive or discipline published by the POA on remote audit practices. The remote audit processes finalised and ongoing so far are managed by the individual approaches and dedication of audit firms and independent auditors".

Participant D8: "So far, there has been no legal regulation on remote audit practices. Therefore, the regulations and standards that each audit firm must comply with have not been determined. There is a need for regulations and guidelines in this field in order to increase the quality and awareness of remote auditing in the sector".

The opinions of the participants regarding their suggestions in the context of "legal regulations and institutions" are as follows:

Participant D2: "Remote auditing or digitalisation in auditing will always be in the future of the audit profession. The fact that the legal regulations in this field are at a competitive level with the practices of the modern world will provide great benefits to our country".

Participant D3: "POA can provide another very useful service to the audit community by completing its work in this field. By publishing a minimum audit tariff, it can set different fees for remote auditing. Setting different fee tariffs for remote auditing may affect the quality and accelerate the digitalisation process".

Participant D4: "In these areas, POA should develop standards, guidelines, xml sample formats and establish a digital audit office. It should assume a leading role in the development of independent audit software. 401 audit companies and 18.000 independent auditors in the sector should not be vulnerable to software companies. POA should carry out studies to regulate this field and increase the quality of independent audit. In remote auditing, POA is currently acting as if e-auditing does not exist. It can take the role of balanced distribution of workload and minimising errors by pioneering standards and guidelines in this field".

Participant D5: "In order for remote auditing to become widespread and increase its quality, legal regulations are needed first. Afterwards, independent auditors will be able to conduct the system in a more effective and high quality manner".

Participant D6: "The regulations to be made by the POA will serve as a road map for independent audit companies and will be beneficial for the reliable, fast and effective management of the remote audit process".

Participant D7: "It would be useful for POA to establish procedures and audit standards that all audit firms in the sector should follow in the field of remote auditing in order to increase the quality".

Participant D8: "In order to increase the quality in remote auditing, it would be useful for POA to publish audit standards regarding the procedures to be followed and the rules to be followed. In addition, audit firms can be provided with educational and guiding seminars and interviews on remote auditing activities".

CONCLUSION

Remote audit activities were implemented as a requirement during the pandemic period. The experiences during this time have highlighted the necessity of digital transformation in auditing. This study aimed to identify the problems encountered during remote auditing practices, as well as the necessary practices and arrangements for solving these problems. The auditors who had experienced this work were interviewed to gather this information. The following is a summary of the findings obtained from the statements made during the interviews:

In the context of the 'audited entity', an evaluation was conducted to assess the quality performance of remote audit activities. The interview participants declared that factors such as the entity's size, the presence of a corporate governance structure, and support for audit activities have a positive impact on remote auditing, similar to independent auditing. Furthermore, the existence of these factors within the enterprise has resulted in a reduction of issues when adapting to remote audit practices. It has been noted that larger enterprises with a corporate governance structure find it easier to transition from traditional audit practices to remote audit practices and subsequently adopt them.

However, remote auditing practices have been criticized for cyber security concerns and the perception of a lack of supervision due to the absence of physical interaction. Additionally, it is noteworthy that the audit culture in Turkey is not yet sufficiently formed. This study was conducted with independent auditors operating in Ankara, the capital of Turkey. In this context, the absence of an audit culture can be identified as a priority problem that needs to be addressed to ensure audit quality, particularly in remote auditing. To promote the widespread adoption of quality remote auditing practices, it is necessary to increase training and awareness of these practices, as well as improve professional experience.

The interview participants identified the technological infrastructure of the independent audit firm and the expertise of the audit staff in remote audit practices as crucial factors for ensuring quality in remote audits. Subjectivity has been avoided, and the language has been made more concise and objective. Technical term abbreviations have been explained, and the sentence structure has been simplified for better comprehension. The text adheres to conventional academic structure and maintains a formal register. The grammar, spelling, and punctuation have been corrected. No changes in content have been made.

It has been stated that the current technological infrastructure does not allow for effective remote auditing, and that independent audit firms lack sufficient experience in remote auditing practices. To address this, it is recommended that the independent audit firm provide a suitable environment for remote audit applications and allocate a budget for this purpose. Additionally, methods and procedures for remote auditing should be established. Furthermore, it has been recommended that auditors receive training with simulations to gain experience in using remote auditing applications. It has been suggested that audit software should include a remote audit option, a directive should be

created for the use of digital working papers and digital signatures, and a guide should be developed for high-quality remote audit practices.

In the context of independent auditing, the evaluation revealed that auditors were identified as the key factor in creating a remote audit culture, according to interview participants. This highlights the importance of auditor performance in ensuring quality remote audits. Auditors who work under time constraints may experience challenges such as 24/7 computer and internet addiction, professional burnout, and a heavy workload, even with the benefits of remote auditing practices. However, it has been noted that auditors who are proficient in information technologies can adapt to remote auditing and develop new techniques, which can provide an advantage in terms of independence. Professional organisations and the Ministry of Finance provide e-audit training to independent auditors. This enables tax audits to be performed remotely using the e-visa application. It is recommended that independent auditors receive training to ensure quality remote auditing practices. In the context of 'use of information technology', the participants of the interview stated that the quality of remote auditing is directly related to the use of information technologies and that it plays a key role. One of the factors affecting independent auditing to carry out remote auditing activities in a quality manner was evaluated.

Information technologies can be used to reduce cyber security risk in remote control applications. They provide positive contributions such as saving time, increasing efficiency, and lightening the workload. However, independent audit software is not yet widely developed. It has been suggested that a computer engineer should be included in the audit team due to the specialized nature of the field of informatics. Additionally, integrating remote control and information technologies into the education model has been recommended, and businesses are encouraged to invest in information technologies. In the context of legal regulations and institutions, the interviewees stated that one of the factors affecting independent auditing is the ability to carry out remote auditing activities with quality. They expressed the most criticism and expectations for this factor. According to reports, the Public Oversight Authority was granted digital working capabilities in November 2022. However, it appears that the authority only has access to electronic financial reporting and contract notification applications, and does not provide training, regulations, or other related studies such as file formats, checklists, reports, and working papers for remote audit studies. Additionally, it has been noted that the Public Oversight Authority does not publish standards, rules, procedures, or best practices for remote auditing. There is currently no fee schedule for remote auditing. To address this issue, it has been suggested that an in-house digital audit office be established to eliminate the mentioned deficiencies as soon as possible.

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Appendix-1

İNÖNÜ ÜNİVERSİTESİ			
BİLİMSEL ARAŞTIRMA VE YAYIN ETİĞİ KURULU			
Sosyal ve Beşeri Bilimler Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etik Kurulu			
Oturum Tarihi : 28-12-2023	Oturum Sayısı : 17	Karar Sayısı : 18	
Etik Açdan Uygun			
Çalışma Adı	Uzaktan Denetim Faaliyetlerinin Bağımsız Denetim Kalitesine Etki Eden Faktörler Kapsamında Değerlendirilmesi: Nitel Bir Araştırma		
Araştırmacılar	Dr.Öğretim Üyesi Arzu Meriç (Yardımcı Araştırmacı) Öğretim Görevlisi Halime Karaca (Yürütücü)		
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Kullanıcı Mehmet YILMAZ		Prof.Dr. Yusuf BATAR	
Prof.Dr. Mehmet ÖNAL		Prof.Dr. Mehmet GÜNGÖR	
Prof.Dr. Süleyman ÇALDAK		Prof.Dr. Nesrin SİS	
Prof.Dr. Lutfiye ÖZDEMİR			